

Priyanka Ghode *et al*, International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Applications,
Vol.10 Issue. 10, October- 2022, pg. 51-58

ISSN: 2321-8363

Impact Factor: 6.308

(An Open Accessible, Fully Refereed and Peer Reviewed Journal)

A Review: College Enquiry Automated Chatbot

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7310856](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7310856)

Abstract: A chatbot is a software that's use is diverse in today's world it is used to interact between a computer and a human in natural language like humans chat. Chatbots chat with the user in a conversation in place of a human and reply to the user. A college enquiry chatbot to be used by students to get their queries responded easily from the college website The main aim of the research presented in this paper was conduct a systematic review of high-quality journal research papers in order to summarize the current state of research on chatbot .The future work include training the chatbot with more varied data, increasing the scope of the chatbot by adding a speech recognition speech recognition feature so that users can speak to get responses, and including integration with multiple channels such as phone call, SMS, and various social media platforms.

Keywords: chatbot, NLP, Enquiry

I. Introduction

Presently chatbot is most useful in education System. Chatbot was an application which may speak to human beings naturally and resolve student queries, the way we interact with one another. It can replace a person's for several tasks of answering queries. The proposed chat bot is Rule based a NLP chatbot used to provide service to the user who can query any college related activities through the system. The system analyses the question and then answers to the student as if a human is interacting. The important keywords from the query will be fetched from the knowledge base. If the match is found the relevant

answer will be provided to the student or the default message will be shown to the user that “Answer to this query is not available at this moment, please revert back after sometime”.

The “Keyword Matching” algorithm will be used to match the keywords from the knowledge base. If student doesn't get satisfying answer he will mark the answer, administrator will handle that question, he get message as not satisfying answer. To access this chatbot, user needs to have a web services enabled device. The system proposed system will be a web based system. If user has a decent internet connection, he/she will get the answers to his/her queries in the usual time which answer by its knowledge base.. As students, we require many types of information regarding our college and university during our course. Sometimes getting this information is rather cumbersome and lengthy Like getting information regarding our fees structure or the due fees remaining is a very lengthy process we have to go to administration building and find the correct window and then look for a no dues form then fill it with correct data and then submit it to the appropriate person and then that person will tell us our due fees. This is all long, hectic and unnecessary. We live in an age of computer science, where automation and simple procedures are easy to achieve. So why have this long and unnecessary process to get this trivial information. We as a computer science student are always looking forward to solving the problems around us using the technology that we learn and how to implement them to achieve ease of usage in real life. This is where we thought of using an intelligent chat bot delivering this information. Think about an application, where all you have to do is chat. You want to know the fee structure of a student, then ask the chatbot about is it clear or not it will tell you. There is no need of doing a lengthy and hectic procedure. If You want to know the process of filling the university exam form, no problem our bot will tell you the steps. It can also solve the dilemma when a student is about to join the college. He/she may want to enquire about the fee structure of various colleges and know their admission procedure. Now in the current system, it can be a long process. You would have to go to various college sites and then check it. Then chatbot can do it for you in seconds all you will have to do is to ask it. Isn't it easy and convenient?.

II. Types OF Chatbot

Fundamentally there are different types of chatbots, in general we can distinguish between three types of chatbots, Rule based, AI based and Hybrid.

- 1) Rule Based:- The rule based chatbot is ideal for where, queries of user are already known and there is repetitive same type of inquiries. These chatbot triggered when some of keywords are entered by user. These type of chatbot developer need to cover as much as user queries.

- 2) AI Based:- These chatbots can grasp the context of chat and determine meaning of user queries. These types of chatbots are connected centralized database. It can also recall previous interactions and use that information to maintain congruity.
- 3) Hybrid:- Hybrid chatbot is combination both chatbot. Hybrid chatbot provide an automated chat conversation and attempts to resolve users query quickly and simple as possible.

III. RELATED WORK

In literature, these are some previous works related to chatting systems or chatbot for universities. Online Chatting System for college in queries using a knowledgeable database by Bathe, Malusare, and Kolpe is doing pattern matching to perform information retrieval on chatbots. It has not already used the deep learning approach, so that is still too rigid by rules for users to make inquiries. But, detailed working steps in this research are very good.[1].

Erasmus the AI chatbot, Erasmus is a chatbot on Facebook which is used to answer the queries related to the college information. Designing end-to-end systems using cloud services, starting from api.ai (Dialogflow), Mlab (MongoDB cloud), IBM Bluemix (webhook API), scraper import.io to minimize the

scripting code process, but what's happening here, it is all because there are too many diverse cloud services, there is quite a long latency between the services [2].

Intelligent Chatbot System Based on Entity Extraction Using RASA NLU and Neural Network by Anran Jiao was comparing performance between RASA NLU stack with Neural Network Classifier and Entity Extractor from scratch. This research was told that the RASA NLU method still superior to extract all the entities and classify user speech intent. It's also quite comprehensive research [3] to all those previous works, this research will be more reliable by using rule based chatbot natural language understanding and need for pattern matching.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEMS

A college enquiry chatbot project will developed with the help of python that is widely used that analyzes user's queries and user's message. The proposed System could be a internet based chatbot that provides answers to the queries provided by the student or the user. Users will merely question through the chatbot that's used for chatting. Students will chat by using any format there's no specific format the user needs to follow.

The answers are applicable what the user queries. If the answers are found to be invalid or not accessible than those queries are to be marked. Later those queries can updated by the admin, just in case of urgency we are going to provides a message that "our representatives will get in touch with you shortly". The User will raise any faculty connected activities through the system. The user doesn't ought to in person move to the faculty for enquiry. The System analyzes the question and so answers to the user. The system answers to the question as if it's answered by the person. The system replies with the help of a good Graphical interface which suggests that as if a true person is reprehension the user.

1. System Model

2. Working Model

V. Benefits

- i. ChatBots have 24/7 availability: chatbots can be available to solve students problem 24/7.
- ii. Chatbots provide long term Financial Savings: universities that have human student help teams have to pay large amount of money as salaries.
- iii. Facilate seamless live communication.
- iv. For the User, there is no need to visit the college personally to enquiry about the college related information.

V. This system aids the students to be updated with college related activities.

Vi. This system is developed aiming at reducing the time for the student, parents as well as the faculty at the institution

VI. Limitations of chatbot

i. Chatbot does not understand human context.

ii. Accuracy: Chatbots are designed to have a human-like conversation to perform a mission. Current chatbots, however, have a weak propensity to change the subject responses. It reacts without meaning often. Accuracy is therefore not achieved at a sufficient stage.

iii. Chatbots have the same answer for a query

iv. They have zero research skills. Grammatical Errors: Grammatical errors are not remembered.

v. Structure of the Language: Each language has a different structure of sentence making. The arrangement of documents, punctuation and the use of spaces, for instance, vary between languages. It cannot be distinguished from current chatbots.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this article, a number of selected articles have been covered in the literature review, concentrating primarily on types Chatbots of in the recent time.. From the above study, due to the range of methods and approaches used to build a Chatbot, it can be said that the growth and advancement of Chatbot design is not increasing at a predictable pace. In general, limited to unique applications. By developing more robust knowledge bases, general-purpose chatbots need improvements. Furthermore, chatbots needs to be developed by extending the data and more features for helping the automating task in the universities, then by directing towards the open domain chatbot, for more extensive implementation in deep learning Chatbot,. Also the needs for implementing chatbot within no limitations and more customizable

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